

MODELLING-BASED PROOF-OF-CONCEPT FOR Ca(OH)₂- ENHANCED CO₂ CAPTURE IN A CALCIUM LOOPING PROCESS

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Abstract

Scenarios in which global warming is limited to 1.5 °C require some form of carbon dioxide removal technologies. Calcium looping (CaL) is an emerging CO₂ capture process in which CaO is cycled between two CFB reactors: the carbonator, in which CO₂ is adsorbed, forming CaCO₃, and the calciner, in which the sorbent is regenerated. The carbonator is typically operated at a temperature close to 650 °C and with CO₂ capture efficiencies of around 90 %. This modelling study assesses a concept to improve the CO₂ capture efficiency of the CaL process to 99 %.

The investigated carbonator design employs a larger heat exchanger to attain a temperature drop of 100 °C over the height of the reactor. This results in a temperature of approximately 550 °C in the top region of the carbonator, thus reducing the minimum CO₂ concentration achievable according to the CO₂-CaO equilibrium. In addition, calcium hydroxide is fed in the upper part of the reactor as an additional sorbent to capture part of the remaining CO₂.

An in-house model is used to simulate the interconnected reactors, represented one-dimensionally by control volumes along their heights. The model features comprehensive reaction modelling, with heterogeneous and homogeneous combustion and sorbent reactions expressed by kinetic equations. Semi-empirical closure models are used for fluidised bed hydrodynamics and heat transfer.

First, a steady state balance measured in the “La Pereda” pilot is simulated and serves as a reference point. Then, a calcium hydroxide injection is added, and the resulting temperature and CO₂ profiles are compared with those of the reference case. The resulting CO₂ capture efficiency of the carbonator increases from 93 % close to 99 %.

Based on the model results, the investigated carbonator configuration offers a significant potential to further reduce CO₂ emissions in industrial processes. The parameters controlling the sorbent reaction rates will be calibrated with experimental data from pilot tests once available, and the validated model will be used in future large-scale studies.

Keywords: circulating fluidised bed, carbon capture, calcium looping, calcium hydroxide.

1. Introduction

Carbon capture technologies are needed to reduce emissions in hard-to-abate sectors (FCCC, 2023) such as the cement, steel and iron, and power sectors. Calcium looping is a tail-end method used to capture carbon dioxide (CO₂) by blowing flue gas through a bed rich in calcium oxide (CaO) (Shimizu, et al., 1999) in a CFB reactor. The CO₂ reacts with the CaO particles, forming calcium carbonate (CaCO₃), and is then circulated to a second reactor in which it is

decomposed back to CaO and CO₂, producing a concentrated stream of CO₂ that can be utilized or stored after purification. Heat is provided to the process by firing a solid fuel in the calciner, and excess heat is removed from the carbonator by heat-exchanging surfaces. Reactor conditions are dictated by the CaO-CO₂ equilibrium curve (Abanades, et al., 2015): calcining the sorbent in a stream of concentrated CO₂ under atmospheric pressure requires a temperature of 900 °C, while reducing the CO₂ concentration of the treated gas below 0.1 %-v requires a temperature of around 550 °C. However, the highest carbon capture efficiencies, defined as the ratio of CO₂ captured to the total flow of CO₂ entering the carbonator, are typically reached at temperatures between 600 and 650 °C due to the effect of temperature on the kinetics of carbonation (Dieter, et al., 2013) and the maximum carbonation conversion (Criado, et al., 2018). The equilibrium CO₂ concentration at 650 °C is 1 %-v, which corresponds to a maximum carbon capture efficiency of 90 % when treating typical flue gases with a CO₂ concentration of 10 %-v.

A method to reach a carbon capture efficiency of 99 % has been proposed (Arias, et al., 2022; CaLby2030, 2022). It consists of operating the dense bed, where most of the CO₂ is captured, at a temperature close to 650 °C and installing additional heat-transfer surfaces to reduce the temperature in the top region of the carbonator to 550 °C. This would, in principle, allow for the CO₂ capture in the dense bed to be maximized, while an injection of highly reactive calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂) in the dilute upper region of the carbonator would capture most of the remaining CO₂, potentially increasing the total carbon capture efficiency of the carbonator to 99 %.

This paper presents a proof-of-concept for the method described. A steady-state balance measured at the La Pereda pilot is modelled and the effect of implementing a Ca(OH)₂ injection is simulated by using interconnected 1D reactor models. The study quantifies the CO₂ reduction achievable under partial load conditions and a suitable temperature profile.

2. Methodology

The reactor model used in the proof-of-concept study is a dynamic 1D CFB model developed at LUT (Ylätaalo, et al., 2012). The reactor is divided vertically into control volumes for which time-dependent heat and mass balances are written, and the obtained set of differential equations is solved by the ODE solvers available in the Simulink environment. While dynamic simulations are supported by the model, in this work the reactor system is evaluated at a steady state by running the simulation to convergence. The model features homogeneous and heterogeneous chemical reactions, and the most relevant of the gas-solid reactions are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Selected heterogeneous reactions. Reaction rates r_i in kg/s.

Reaction	Equation	ΔH_{298K} [kJ/mol]	Ref.
Calcination	$\text{CaCO}_3(\text{s}) \rightarrow \text{CaO}(\text{s}) + \text{CO}_2(\text{g})$ $r_{\text{calc}} = k_{\text{calc}} n_{\text{Ca}} M_{\text{CaCO}_3} X_{\text{carb}}^{0.67} (C_{\text{CO}_2, \text{eq}} - C_{\text{CO}_2})$ $k_{\text{calc}} = 2057 \exp(-112400/RT)$ $C_{\text{CO}_2, \text{eq}} = 4.137 \times 10^{12} / RT \exp(-20474/RT)$	178.2	(Fang, et al., 2009) (Martínez, et al., 2012) (Stanmore & Gilot, 2005)
Carbonation	$\text{CaO}(\text{s}) + \text{CO}_2(\text{g}) \rightarrow \text{CaCO}_3(\text{s})$ $r_{\text{carb}} = k_{\text{carb}} n_{\text{Ca}} X_{\text{CaO}}^{0.1} M_{\text{CaO}} (X_{\text{max}} - X_{\text{CaCO}_3})^{0.67} (C_{\text{CO}_2} - C_{\text{CO}_2, \text{eq}})$ $k_{\text{carb}, \text{CaCO}_3} = 0.3429 \exp(-2309/T)$ $k_{\text{carb}, \text{Ca(OH)}_2} = 70 \exp(-2309/T)$	-178.2	Adapted from (Grasa, et al., 2009)
Dehydration	$\text{Ca(OH)}_2 \rightarrow \text{CaO}(\text{s}) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{g})$ $r_{\text{dehy}} = k_{\text{dehy}} n_{\text{Ca}} M_{\text{Ca(OH)}_2} X_{\text{Ca(OH)}_2}^{0.67}$ $k_{\text{dehy}} = 4359 \exp(-63200/RT)$	109.2	(Arias, et al., 2022)

The kinetic behaviour of the carbonation of Ca(OH)_2 is known to be complex (Koga & Kodani, 2018), but in this study, it was assumed to consist of the dehydration of Ca(OH)_2 followed by the carbonation of the nascent CaO . The rate constant for the carbonation of Ca(OH)_2 -derived CaO was obtained by fitting the reaction model to the results of a drop-tube experiment similar to that presented in Arias et al. (2022). A full description of the remaining reactions is presented by Ritvanen et al. (2021).

The empirical correlation of Johnsson & Leckner (1995) is used to define the density profile of the main sorbent in the reactor, which is assumed to have a uniform particle size of 120 μm . The auxiliary sorbent injected in the dilute top region of the reactor is assumed to initially consist of a fine (10 μm) Ca(OH)_2 powder and to be in plug flow. The main sorbent entrained from the calciner is fully recirculated to the carbonator and vice-versa, whereas the auxiliary sorbent is assumed to leave the system with the gas stream through the cyclone.

A steady-state balance, as measured at the La Pereda pilot (Diego & Arias, 2020), was simulated to establish a reference case. This serves as a basis for comparing the effects of the Ca(OH)_2 injection. The reference case and the case with the Ca(OH)_2 injection will be referred to as C1 and C2, respectively. The pilot consists of two 15 m tall cylindrical reactors, with internal diameters of 0.65 and 0.75 m for the carbonator and calciner, respectively. The carbonator is cooled by four bayonet tubes hanging from the roof down to an elevation of 3 m above the grid. Because the temperature in the upper part of the carbonator was already suitable for highly efficient CO_2 capture, i.e., close to 550 $^\circ\text{C}$, additional cooling surfaces were not needed and the Ca(OH)_2 was injected at the relatively high temperature of 350 $^\circ\text{C}$, thus minimizing changes in the temperature profiles of both reactors. For this study, an injection elevation of 5 m and a $\text{Ca(OH)}_2/\text{CO}_2$ molar ratio of 3 were chosen, where the flow of CO_2 refers to the flow exiting the carbonator in the reference case. The boundary conditions of the simulated reactors are given in Table 2, and the specifications of the fired coal are given in Table 3.

Table 2. Boundary conditions of simulated reactors.

Parameter	Unit	Carbonator	Calciner
Heat exchange area	m^2	5.75	-
Hydroxide injection, C1 / C2	kg/s	0 / 0.022	-
Fuel consumption	MW_{LHV}	-	1.49
Cooling duty	kW	200	-
Heat losses, reactor walls	kW	50	50
Fluidising gas flow	kg/s	0.31	0.45
Fluidising gas O_2	m-%	3.3	23.3
Fluidising gas N_2	m-%	67.5	76.7
Fluidising gas CO_2	m-%	18.9	-
Fluidising gas H_2O	m-%	10.2	-
Fluidising gas SO_2	m-%	0.14	-
Fluidising gas temperature	$^\circ\text{C}$	115	25
Loop seal air flow	kg/s	0.11	0.12
Make-up flow	kg/s	-	0.1
Make-up CaCO_3	m-%	-	98.6
Make-up inert	m-%	-	1.4
Density of solids	kg/m^3	2000	2000
CO_2 carrying capacity of sorbent (X_{max}), main / aux.	mol/mol	0.13 / 0.7	-
Bed pressure	Pa	8700	2300

Table 3. Specifications of the coal fired.

LHV MJ/kg, a.r.	Proximate analysis, m-%, a.r.				Ultimate analysis, m-%, d.a.f.				
	Moisture	Ash	Char	Volatiles	C	H	N	S	O
26.43	1.9	20.3	54.8	23.0	86.4	5.4	1.7	2.0	4.5

3. Results and discussion

The temperature and pressure profiles of both reactors are presented in Fig. 1, showing good agreement between experimental results and the simulation. The reference case was a partial load case, with grid gas velocities close to 2.5 m/s and a low suspension density in the upper parts of the reactors. The bottom region of the calciner is cooler due to the endothermic calcination reaction and the thermal mass of solids recirculated from the carbonator, while the carbonator has a more pronounced temperature gradient due to the installed cooling surfaces. The dashed lines show that the temperature and pressure profiles do not change dramatically when $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ is injected. The applied $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2/\text{CO}_2$ ratio leads to a net endothermic effect from the combined dehydration and carbonation reactions of the auxiliary sorbent. This, in conjunction with its relatively low feeding temperature, causes the temperature in the carbonator to decrease slightly.

Fig. 1. Temperature and pressure profiles. Squares: measured values; Solid lines: reference case (C1); Dashed lines: simulated $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ injection (C2). Black: calciner; Grey: carbonator.

The CO_2 the carbonation rate profiles are shown in Fig. 2. The graphs show how the partial pressure of CO_2 quickly decreases to 1 kPa in the dense bed, which is close to the equilibrium pressure. Above the dense bed, the bayonet tubes reduce the suspension temperature and, consequently, the equilibrium pressure of CO_2 . However, due to the low concentration of solids, additional capture above the dense bed is limited and the pressure of CO_2 does not decrease below 0.7 kPa. The resulting carbon capture efficiency of 93 % is in good agreement with the values measured under similar conditions, which were between 85 and 96 %.

Fig. 2. CO_2 pressure and carbonation profiles of the carbonator.

When the results of C1 are compared to those of C2, the effect of the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ injection is clearly visible as a sharp reduction in CO_2 concentration above the injection point. The CO_2 concentration decreases from 0.9 %-v at 5 m to approximately 0.1 %-v at 15 m, resulting in an overall carbon capture efficiency of 98.6 %. The CO_2 and carbonation profiles indicate that the auxiliary sorbent has sufficient contact time with the gas for efficient carbonation, although a longer residence time might have yielded a slight improvement in the carbon capture efficiency. While the reactor model encompasses only the CFB riser, in a real plant the contact time of the auxiliary sorbent would be extended at least until the cyclone, but possibly as far as the baghouse, further increasing the amount of CO_2 captured.

The carbonation profiles of Fig. 2b also show that the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ injection suppresses the carbonation of the main sorbent in the upper part of the carbonator by consuming the CO_2 available. While carbonation in the freeboard of the reactor was not very significant for the overall carbon capture efficiency of the reference case studied, this could change when operating the reactor at full load, as a leaner bed and a denser freeboard would likely cause carbonation in the entrained zone to become more prominent. This could lead to a scenario where injecting the auxiliary sorbent at a higher elevation would be more efficient, as the main sorbent would be able to capture a larger share of CO_2 despite the carbonation of the auxiliary sorbent being limited.

4. Conclusion

A method to increase the carbon capture efficiency of a calcium looping process was studied using interconnected 1D reactor models. The results show that sufficient contact time is needed between the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and flue gases for efficient CO_2 capture. They also suggest that the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ injection can suppress the carbonation of the main sorbent, and while this had a negligible effect on the overall carbon capture efficiency under the conditions examined, the effect could be more significant under full load conditions. Overall, the simulation results support the feasibility of the configuration studied and suggest that carbon capture efficiencies as high as 99 % could be reached under the right conditions, although the limitations of the study must be acknowledged. There is little experimental data available on the kinetics of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ under the conditions studied, i.e., at temperatures close to 550°C and CO_2 concentrations close to equilibrium, and the hydrodynamic interactions between the main and auxiliary sorbents have not been studied in detail. Additionally, while the model assumes perfectly mixed control volumes, achieving sufficient dispersion of the auxiliary sorbent in the radial direction could pose a practical challenge, especially in large-scale units. A better understanding of the behaviour of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ under CFB conditions will hopefully be reached once data from upcoming experimental campaigns becomes available, allowing the model to be properly validated and calibrated.

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